

Supplementary Figure S2. Gas volume within Gouda cheese wheels made using the conventional (A, B, E, F) and bioprotective (C, D, G, H) starter cultures with (E, F, G, H) and without (A, B, C, D) inoculation with *Paucilactobacillus wasatchensis* SK0033 (4 log CFU/mL) and aged at 4°C, 10°C, or 15°C for 37-40 weeks. Calculated gas volume percentage of cheese wheels using three-dimensional image analysis. Data points represent the calculated gas volume percent in each cheese wheel. Solid black horizontal line indicates the mean calculated gas volume per cheese wheel for each replicated cheesemake. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD post-hoc tests were used to determine statistical differences of starter culture and inoculation status for each aging temperature. Cheeses that do not share at least one capital letter at the same aging temperature are significantly different (p -value < 0.05).